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Practicality Evaluation of Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) – Micro Gas Turbine (MGT) Hybrid Power Generation System

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Abstract

Solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) and micro gas turbine (MGT) hybrid power generation system (SOFC-MGT HPGS) is highly expected as one of the key technologies which can achieve energy saving and less CO₂ emission for a sustainable low-carbon society.

Mitsubishi Hitachi Power Systems Co., Ltd. (MHPS) has developed a 250kW-class SOFC-MGT HPGS for market introduction, and practicality evaluation from a user-side view with multiple evaluation points is required towards wide-spread use of such systems.

Here, we practically evaluate the newly developed SOFC-MGT HPGS including basic performance, system safety, environmental properties of noise and exhaust, and long-term durability under various environmental conditions through various kinds of field tests of the developed systems. As the results, we have confirmed high performance and sufficient applicability of the system, which led to deregulation of operators' continuous monitoring and the world's first market introduction and commercialization of SOFC-MGT HPGS.

Fig.1 Field test of SOFC-MGT HPGS (NEXT-FC, Kyushu University)

Fig.2 Over 20,000-h field test data of SOFC-MGT HPGS at NEXT-FC, Kyushu University

Introduction

Under the actualizing global warming effect, it is indispensable and urgent to develop a highly efficient power generation system that contributes to the simultaneous realization of energy saving and low-carbon fossil fuel utilization. As an effective solution to this issue, a hybrid power generation system combining solid-oxide fuel cells and micro gas turbine is expected to put into practical use and introduced into the market [1].

However, in order to put newly developed power generation system into practical and widespread use, it is necessary to evaluate its' practicality and social benefit from a user-side perspective [2]. For user-side evaluation of new technology, it is quite important to verify not only basic performance, but also safety including the event of anomalies, environmental properties such as noise and emissions, long-term durability and reliability including robustness to environmental changes such as air temperature, rain, and snow, etc.

In this study, various practicability evaluation tests were carried out on SOFC-MGT HPGS developed by MHPS using several demonstration systems with different installation and operation conditions. Through long-term field tests of the systems, practicability of the developed SOFC-MGT technology were confirmed, that leads to the world's first commercialization of SOFC-MGT HPGS through an installation at a building in Tokyo.

1. Practicality Evaluation

In this study, various evaluations were conducted using three systems shown in Figure 1.

In October 2012, the first prototype system was installed in a building at Tokyo Gas test site. Long-term continuous rated power generation in an indoor installation environment and safety verification tests were conducted in the event of an anomaly in preparation for review of deregulation of continuous monitoring regulations of the Electrical Utilities Act in Japan.

A new SOFC-MGT HPGS powered by improved cell stack was installed outdoors at Next-Generation Fuel Cell Research Center at Kyushu University in March 2015. Long-term rated power generation has been carried out including a long-term durability evaluation that consists of environmental robustness with extreme hot and humid condition in summer, heavy snow in winter, typhoons, heavy rains, and big earthquakes.

Furthermore, in 2016, the same type was installed at the indoor test site of Tokyo Gas, and various evaluations such as the basic performance and load-following performance evaluation as a cogeneration system, the evaluation of the durability against repeated normal startup and abnormal shutdown.

Fig. 1 Test systems for practicality evaluations

(Indoor prototype at Tokyo Gas, Outdoor system at Kyushu Univ., Indoor system at Tokyo Gas)

2. Practicality Evaluation Method

To evaluate the practicality of a power generation system, not only its basic performance, but safety, durability, and reliability under actual operation conditions are quite important. Confirming the state of compliance with relevant regulations related to national or international codes and standards are also required for proper installation and operation. Therefore, evaluation tests were performed and results were evaluated judged on the basis of regulations and standards for related system such as JIS C 8841-2 "Small Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Systems-Part 2: Safety Standards and Safety Testing Methods" [3] and JIS C 8841-3 "Small Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Systems-Part 3: Performance Testing Methods and Environmental Testing Methods" [4]. However, these standards apply to small scale systems (rated power less than 10 kW), and are intended for installation in houses or small buildings. Furthermore, these standards are not applied to pressurized SOFC module and combined system with gas turbines. Therefore, this study also evaluate and verify the applicability of existing test methods and standards of small stationary SOFC systems to large-scale pressurized SOFC-MGT hybrid power generation systems.

In this study, we proposed multi-point evaluation including not only basic performance and safety, but also operability such as durability and environmental durability of 10-year-actual indoor or outdoor operation. The following is a summary of the main items for evaluation.

2.1 Rated Operation Performance

In evaluating the performance of a power generation system, the output and efficiency at rated operation are the most important indicators. In this study, the basic performance was evaluated based on the standard performance test method specified by JIS C 8841-3. The rated power generation status was maintained for 3 hours or more with the rated power generation held for 3 hours or more, and the total electric output of the hybrid power generation system measured at the outlet of the inverter of the power generation unit for 3 hours, and the time average data was taken as the power generation output. During the measurement of the output, the flow rate of city gas flowing through the Azbil Kimmon Co., Ltd.'s Gas Meter RA65TPCK. The flow rate was converted to the standard condition using the data of temperature and pressure of the gas.

Power generation efficiency was calculated by measured output power and gas flow rate. Regarding the exhaust heat recovery performance, water was circulated to the exhaust gas heat exchanger attached to the exhaust gas line, and the amount of waste heat recovery was calculated from the circulating water temperature and circulating water flow rate at the inlet and outlet of the heat exchanger. The exhaust heat recovery efficiency was also calculated from gas flow rate. In this study, the basic performance evaluation was carried out by the improved demonstration system installed in 2016 at Tokyo Gas test site.

2.2 Load Following Performance

Load variable range and load following speed of power generation systems are becoming to an important performance for output-adjusting distributed power sources in the future of unstable renewable energy popularization. This performance was also evaluated according to the load following characteristics test of JIS C 8841-3. In this test, the load was decreased to the 50 % of the rated output, which is the lowest load of this system, and the load-following-ability at the time of load decreasing was evaluated by the

time from the start of load decreasing operation at the rated power generation to the arrival of the indicated output.

In addition, by keeping 50 % output for 3 hours or more, after evaluating and confirming the stability of the system in the lowest load operation, an operation to increase the load to the rated output was taken, and the load-following-ability at the time of load increase was evaluated by the time from the start of load increasing operation to reaching the rated output.

2.3 Environmental Friendliness

In evaluation of the effect of the power generation system to the surrounding environment is also quite important for social implementation. The cleanliness of the exhaust gas, such as the concentration of nitrogen oxides (NO_x), unburned hydrocarbons (THC), sulfur oxides (SO_x), and dust, as well as noise and vibration generated during operation are important evaluation index, which should be referred to local regulations, codes, and standards.

Among these items, the exhaust gas property was evaluated based on the JIS environmental test methods by measuring the concentrations of NO_x and THC using exhaust gas analyzer MEXA-7100 of Horiba Co., Ltd.,. Hazardous substances such as sulfur oxides and dust are also analyzed using gas chromatograph by Chugai Technos Co., Ltd.

In order to measure the noise and vibration under the condition of minimizing background noise and vibration, we measured the noise and vibration under the steady condition of the rated power generation in accordance with the environmental test methods stipulated in JIS C 8841-3 using the test system installed at the indoor test site of Tokyo Gas. Specifically, noise levels at steady-state power generation were measured by using a sound level meter NL-52 manufactured by Rion Co., Ltd. by setting 16 measuring points so as to surround the power generation system, using a position of 1 m on the generator side and 1.2 m in height as a measuring point. Further, surface vibration of the power generation system near the noise measurement point is analyzed with attaching element of the vibration meter VA-12 manufactured by Rion Co., Ltd.

2.5 System Safety under Normal Operation

Although it is important that the power generation system has beneficial basic performance, it is necessary to operate safely even in the case of various environmental and operational conditions. Therefore, safety in normal operation is an important evaluation item that should be verified in an actual installation and operational conditions before market introduction.

In particular, SOFC-MGT HPGS must have adequate safety measures in the power generation system because cell stack is operated at a high temperature of around 900 °C, and highly-reactive hydrogen and toxic carbon monoxide, which is at risk of generating gas poisoning in the event of a leak. In addition to these hazards, the system also has the additional hazards of pressurized SOFC operation and hybrid power generation using MGT.

Therefore, the surface temperature and exhaust gas temperature were measured from the viewpoint of fire and burn prevention, and the composition of the exhaust gas was analyzed from the viewpoint of confirming the risk of carbon monoxide poisoning. All of index are evaluated through comparing the existing national and international codes and standards.

2.6 System Safety in the Event of Internal Error

Regarding the safety evaluation of power generation systems, it is necessary not only to evaluate the systems during normal operation, but also abnormal condition including shutdown due to internal malfunction or external troubles. Considering SOFC-MTG HPGS with pressurized SOFC, the module stores more amount of high-temperature hazardous gases than non-pressurized systems, which could lead to higher risk and more damage in accidents.

Therefore, safety verification in case of internal error in the actual system was also carried out. To verify system safety under the most severe accidental condition, we intentionally input a signal of internal abnormality occurrence shifting to emergency shutdown mode during rated power operation and analyzed transition of operation data after error detection.

2.7 Safety in the Event of External Disturbance Error

Regarding abnormal occurrences during operation, abnormalities of external environment at the installation site, such as lightning blackouts or earthquakes, should be considered. It is also necessary to maintain safety even in the event of such conditions.

In this study, long-term outdoor power generation demonstration was conducted at Kyushu University to accumulate data of various external error conditions. As a specific example, we evaluated the data obtained when a big earthquake with seismic intensity of 4 was observed at the installation site during the Kumamoto Earthquake that occurred in April 2016.

2.8 Long-term Durability under Various Environmental Conditions

It is also important that the performance and safety of a power generation system can be maintained over a life time of the system. In addition, this long-term durability needs to include robustness to various environmental conditions. Especially for outdoor installed systems, stable operation and performance maintenance are required even under various environmental changes such as rising temperature and humidity in summer, heavy rain and strong wind in the case of typhoons, and snow coverage in winter. This item was also evaluated through long-term outdoor field test at Kyushu University.

2.9 Normal Start and Stop Cycle Durability

In the actual operation of the power generation systems, the periodic inspection and maintenance work of the system should be required based on the operating plan. Scheduled stopping according to the installation environment or needs of the users should be considered during life-time operation. Therefore, it is necessary to confirm the durability of normal start-up and shutdown operation cycle during the operation period because thermal cycling of SOFC deteriorates the materials and structures of cell stacks, resulting in performance degradation or malfunction of power generation system.

In this study, we evaluated the durability of SOFC cell stack by performing 30-time-repeated start and stop operations with assuming that a relatively large number of normal shutdowns and restarts are performed (3 times a year in estimated life time of 10 years). Specifically, after starting from the cold state of the power generation system and continuing the rated power generation for 3 hours or more to obtain the operation data, the shutdown operation was performed to automatically shut down the power generation module, including the cell stack, and after confirming that the maximum temperature in the

power generation module, including the fuel cell stack, had shifted to the shutdown completion state of 100 °C or less. The power output transition and its stability during the rated power generation from the first time to 30 times and the durability against repeated start-ups and shutdown were evaluated and verified.

2.10 Abnormal Shut-down and Restart Cycle Durability

In the actual use of power generation systems, a certain times of emergency stops due to disturbances such as power outage or earthquakes are also expected. Therefore, it is important to evaluate and confirm the durability of repeated abnormal shutdowns assumed during the operation period. In the emergency stop accompanied with the abnormal conditions, steep current changes due to the load shutdown, such as a sudden change in temperature and gas composition in the cell stack due to the emergency shut-off of the fuel or immediate supply of purge gas are all affective to the cell stack durability.

Therefore, the durability characteristics against repeated abnormal shutdown and restart operation were evaluated based on the operation data of actual abnormal shutdowns and restart which occurred during a long-term demonstration in Kyushu University. The durability was evaluated and verified by comparing the average output power of 3 hours rated power generation before abnormal stop and 3-hour-average output after restarting after abnormal shutdown during rated power generation.

3. Results of Practicality Evaluation

3.1 Rated Operation Performance

Table 1 shows the results of the rated operation performance test. As shown in the table, it was confirmed that this system has a high power generation efficiency of 53.6 % LHV, which is equivalent to the latest 1,000 MW class gas turbine combined power generation, even though the power output is 200 kW class. Unlike large centralized power plants, this power generation system can be introduced as a distributed power source close to the demand area. Therefore, it is not necessary to consider the transmission loss and the risk of grid failures can be reduced, thus enabling highly efficient on-site power generation.

It was also confirmed that this system can be operated as a co-generation system in which 20.5 %LHV waste heat can also be effectively utilized by 85 °C hot water recovering with the use of MGT exhaust heat. Therefore, this system has high potential for energy saving and CO₂ reduction, which can realize an on-site energy supply with a total efficiency of 74.1 %LHV by hybrid power generation and waste heat utilization.

Table 1 System performance at rated-output operation of 15-type SOFC-MGT HPGS.

Fuel input [kW-LHV]	381	City gas:33.8 Nm ³ /h
Electrical power output [kW]	204	SOFC + MGT
Power generation efficiency [%-LHV]	53.6	
Heat recovery output [kW]	87.6	85 °C Hot water
Heat recovery efficiency [%-LHV]	20.5	
Total efficiency [%-LHV]	74.1	

3.2 Load Following Performance

Figure 2 shows the results of load following performance tests of the power generation system. Figure 2 (a) is the result of the load increasing test, and Figure 2 (b) is the result of the load decreasing test. As results of these tests, the load increasing speed of 10.2 kW/min (equivalent to 5.7 %/min of the rated power generation output) and the load

decreasing speed of 10.1 kW/min (equivalent to 5.5 %/min) were confirmed. Those are the same level of existing gas turbine combined power generation system despite of complex system configuration of hybrid power generation system of SOFC and MGT. From the results, it was proven that this system is suitable for distributed power generation with high efficiency and high flexibility which can cope with the increasing unstable renewable energy resources.

3.3 Environmental Friendliness

Table 2 shows the results of noise and vibration characteristics. It was confirmed that the average noise is 66.8 dB-A, which is equivalent to existing power generation systems. The measured vibration was 43.6 dB, which was lower than the sensible vibration of 55 dB.

Table 3 also shows the results of the exhaust gas composition. As shown in the table, NO_x concentration in the exhaust was 1.0 ppm (O₂=16%), that was much less than conventional power generation systems without de-NO_x catalyst. This is because the operating temperature of SOFC and off-gas combustion temperature in MGT are lower than thermal NO_x increasing temperature of 1,500 °C. On the other hand, it was confirmed that the unburned hydrocarbon was 833 ppm-C, the SO_x concentration was less than 0.02 ppm, and the dust concentration was less than 0.0009 g/m³. From these results, it was confirmed that this system has a high environmental property that can be installed even in urban areas.

Table 2 Noise and vibration characteristics of 15-type SOFC-MGT HPGS.

Noise [dB-A]	66.8	Under 70 dB-A
Vibration [dB]	43.6	Under 55 dB

Table 3 Exhaust gas characteristics of SOFC-MGT HPGS.

N ₂ [vol ppm]	81.6	
O ₂ [vol %]	15.2	
CO ₂ [vol %]	3.29	
THC [vol ppm-C]	83.3	O ₂ = 0 %
CO [vol ppm]	25.3	O ₂ = 0 %
NO _x [ppm]	1.0	O ₂ = 16 %
SO _x [ppm]	<0.2	
Dust [g/m ³]	<0.0009	

3.5 System Safety under Normal Operation

Table 4 shows the temperature of the system surface, exhaust gas, and the carbon monoxide concentration in the exhaust gas, which were measured as safety evaluation items during rated power generation. The results shows that all items satisfied the standards for small stationary SOFC systems, which are required higher-safety for residential or small building installation. Generally, SOFC operate at a high temperature, while ensuring the safety with the aim of minimizing heat radiation, the cell stack is covered with a sufficiently thick heat insulating material. Therefore, even if the inside of the module is hot, the temperature on the surface is usually kept around 50 °C, and it was also confirmed that the temperature was 56.5 °C even when the module was exposed to direct sunlight during the daytime in midsummer. At the same time, exhaust gas temperature was 185 °C, which was lower than 260 °C of the safety standard. This result shows that sufficient safety is ensured even in the mono-generation system without heat recovery. In this system, most of the heat of MGT combustor is effectively utilized for the compression and preheating to supply pressurized SOFC cathode air. Therefore, the exhaust temperature of MGT is lower than conventional MGT systems and also lower than safety standard.

The CO concentration in the exhaust gas was also 0.0025 vol% (O₂=0%), well below the safety standard of 0.14 vol% for small SOFC systems to be installed outdoors around houses, etc. This is because reformed CO is not only utilized for SOFC modules, but also well-consumed in MGT combustor and effectively utilized for MGT power generation and heat exchange.

Table 4 Safety validation data during rated-output power operation of SOFC-MGT HPGS.

SOFC module surface temp. [°C] at ambient temp. is 38.2 °C	56.5	≦ 95 °C (Codes of Japanese small scale stationary fuel cell system and IEC)
Exhaust gas temp. [°C] at ambient temp. is 38.2 °C	185	≦ 260 °C (Japanese small scale stationary fuel cell system codes : JEMA)
Exhaust CO concentration [vol%] (O ₂ =0%, 15-minutes-average)	0.0025	< 0.14% (Japanese small scale stationary fuel cell system codes : JEMA)

3.6 System Safety in the Event of Internal Error

Figure 3 shows the transition of the voltage of SOFC cell stack and the temperature and pressure in SOFC module during the "emergency stop mode" in which both inlet and outlet valves of the module are urgently closed. It is clear that in this shutdown mode, SOFC is automatically disconnected from the electrical grid, the current of SOFC becomes zero with an open circuit state, since there is no voltage drop due to the internal resistance, the voltage rises immediately after the emergency stop, the voltage remains because there is an electromotive force due to the gas compositional difference between anode and cathode, and decreases gradually thanks to the sealing. It is also confirmed that there is no sudden voltage change or destabilization that could lead to a safety issue.

Regarding to the temperature transition of the module, it is clear that the temperature gradually decreases because exothermic reaction in SOFC stops since emergency stop. Furthermore, it is also clear that there is no abnormal increase or decrease of SOFC

module pressure. From the results, it is confirmed that this system can automatically and safely stop at an internal error occurrence. We also submitted these safety validation data to a committee that discuss deregulation of the Electrical Utility Act, so that all-time operator's monitoring regulation to pressurized SOFC system have been deregulated, and that enabled easy market introduction and future commercialization of pressurized SOFC power generation systems.

Fig.3 Safety validation data of SOFC-MGT HPGS

3.7 Safety in the Event of External Disturbance Error

As a result of safety verification at the occurrence of external disturbance error, Fig.4 shows output transition before and after big earthquake during the long-term operation in Kyushu University. Despite the seismic intensity of 4 was observed at the installation site, the system stopped safely by immediate detection of system disturbances. At detection of disturbance, the system automatically and promptly disconnected to the grid, while maintaining the temperature of SOFC module by shifting operation mode to the hot-standby state that can be easily and speedy restarted. In the period from detection of disturbance to the transition to the hot stand-by state, no rapid increase in temperature or pressure was observed, and it was confirmed that the safety of the system was also maintained. Furthermore, it was confirmed that the output power is the same as that before the earthquake.

Fig.4 Emergency stop and restart of SOFC-MGT HPGS (Earthquake in Kyushu area)

3.8 Long-term Durability under Various Environmental Conditions

Figure 5 shows the results of long-term power generation demonstration of the system installed outdoors at Kyushu University. Since the system started its power generation in May 2015, power generation operation continued while repeating the emergency shutdown and restart due to various abnormal disturbance with multiple normal shutdown and restart for yearly maintenance. As of June 2020, the long-term rated power generation operation reached to 25,000 hours without exchanging and degradation of SOFC cell stacks. Therefore, it was confirmed that this system should be expected to have sufficient long-term durability including various environmental conditions of outdoor installation.

Fig.5 25,000-hour long-term field test data of the outdoor-installed SOFC-MGT HPGS in Kyushu University

3.9 Normal Start and Stop Cycle Durability

Figure 6 shows the results of the output power transition in the normal start-stop cycling test performed with the system installed in Tokyo Gas. The output power at the time of rated generation shown in the figure is plotted with the average output in the state where the rated generation is held for 3 hours or more according to the JIS performance test method. This evaluation is assuming 3 times a year during 10-year operation, so 30 times of normal startup and shutdown were repeated. It is clear that the rated output power does not drop significantly as the number of restart. Through the test, it was found that the rated power reduction rate at the final startup was only 0.74%. From these results, it was confirmed that this system has excellent thermal cycle tolerance which can sufficiently withstand 10-year operation with several start and stop according to the users request, etc.

Fig.6 Start-and-stop cycle operation data of SOFC-MGT hybrid power generation system

3.10 Abnormal Shutdown and Restart Cycle Durability

Figure 7 shows the result of output power at rated power operation after an abnormality detection shutdown during rated power generation. This evaluation data summarizes the recovery results after various abnormal detection stops due to external and internal factors that occurred during the long-term power generation demonstration in Kyushu University.

As shown in the figure, 17 times shutdown and restart were repeated, but the rated power output did not decrease. It was also confirmed that the rated output power at the latest restoration were only 0.06% below than the first data. Assuming abnormal shutdown occurs once a year during 10-year life time, this system is also expected to have sufficient durability even for abnormal shutdown. As the result of three kinds of durability assessment, it was confirmed that this system can be expected sufficient durability for 10-year actual outdoor operation without exchange of SOFC cell stack.

Fig.7 Unintentional stop-and-restart operation data of SOFC-MGT HPGS

4. Conclusions

A practicability evaluation for commercialization of SOFC-MGT hybrid power generation systems was conducted from a user-side perspective based on 10-year-actual operation. Through evaluation tests using several demonstration systems with different installation and operation conditions, the following results and outcomes have been obtained.

- (1) Evaluated SOFC-MGT hybrid power generation system has a high power generation efficiency of 53.6 %LHV, which is equivalent to the 1,000 MW-class state-of-the-art gas turbine combined cycle despite of 200 kW-class output. It was also confirmed that this system combines excellent energy saving as cogeneration and environmental friendliness with 1.0 ppm NO_x (O₂=16%) concentration in the exhaust gas and lower noise and vibrations than standards that enable installation even in the urban area.
- (2) System safety verification using a demonstration system was also carried out for two cases consists of internal malfunction and external disturbance detection. Through the tests, it was confirmed that system safety based on the relevant standards can be secured in both cases. By utilizing the safety verification data, the continuous-monitoring-regulation for some pressurized SOFC systems were deregulated, that leads to easy installation and operation for commercialization.

- (3) Outdoor demonstration with long-term continuous power generation including environmental durability evaluations has been performed. 25,000-hour outdoor operation with practical 10-year durability evaluations including 30 times start-stop operation and 14 times shutdown and restart operation without stack exchange were also confirmed.
- (4) Through the practicability evaluation tests based on the assumed 10-year outdoor or indoor installation and actual operation, it was confirmed that the evaluated system meets the requirements for commercial and industrial applications, which leads to the world's first SOFC-MGT HPGS commercialization.

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